

MUSICOLOGY

**RESEARCH ON PIANO COURSE DEVELOPMENT IN AN
ETHNIC MINORITY UNIVERSITY**

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: This study examines the integration of ethnic minority cultures into university piano education in China's multi-ethnic and multicultural context. This study examines how piano courses can be enhanced to maintain the characteristics of ethnic minorities while ensuring their cultures are well integrated into mainstream university curricula, enabling minority students to achieve better learning outcomes in piano education. **Methods:** This research extends existing university piano courses based on the ADDIE model and adopts qualitative research methods to develop an extended piano course specifically designed for minority students. The research spanned one semester (16 weeks), during which the extended course was systematically developed and implemented through comprehensive evaluations and feedback collection from experts, teachers, and ethnic minority students at different developmental stages. **Results:** This study examines the positive impact of incorporating minority music repertoire and cultural studies into the extended piano course on minority students' learning outcomes. The analysis demonstrates that students not only improved their musical skills but also experienced strengthened confidence in their national culture. The integration approach successfully addressed the challenges faced by minority students in traditional piano education settings. **Conclusion:** The findings indicate a significant enhancement in both technical piano proficiency and cultural identity among minority students. The extended course model proves effective in bridging the gap between traditional Western piano pedagogy and ethnic minority cultural preservation, fostering a more inclusive educational environment. **Implications:** This research can be advantageous for educators, curriculum developers, and policy makers in multicultural educational contexts. The piano education model promotes active cultural engagement and stimulates holistic learning approaches. Educational institutions can utilize this extended course framework as an educational tool to advance equity and diversity. The findings have significant ramifications for expanding these results to broader educational areas and contributing to the realization of comprehensive equity and diversity in higher education. This study examines the potential for cultural integration in specialized music education.

KEY WORDS

Multiculturalism, Ethnic Minorities, Music Education, Piano.

INTRODUCTION

China is a country of natural diversity and symbiosis, diverse species coexisting, diverse ethnic groups getting along with each other, and social diversity and harmony. The total population of the 55 ethnic minorities is 106 million, of which the Hui, Zhuang, Manchu, Mongolian, Miao, Tibetan, Uyghur, Yi, Tujia, Dai, Buyi, Dong, Yao, Bai, Hani, and Kazakh, with a population of over 1 million, are the 18 ethnic minorities that make up the vast majority of the population. These ethnic minorities are concentrated in the autonomous ethnic areas, which cover a total area of 6.1196 million square kilometres (64% of China's land area) (Wang, 2010).

Differences between ethnic groups are reflected in history, culture, geography, economy and all aspects of life. Among these, the most direct, outward and most recognisable feature is undoubtedly culture. Therefore, maintaining and promoting one's own culture is self-evidently important to the survival and development of any ethnic group. Over the course of long history, the various ethnic groups in China have thrived on this land, adapting and transforming nature with their own hard work, bravery and wisdom (Meng, 2006). While jointly creating and defending the unified multi-ethnic country, they have formed their own unique ethnic characteristics and created a multi-layered, diverse and splendidly colourful ethnic culture with its own characteristics. Its diversity is reflected in all aspects of social life, such as language and writing, festivals and customs, food and clothing (Chen & Li, 2010). The Aba Tibetan and Qiang Autonomous Prefecture in Sichuan, for example, is home to a majority of Tibetan and Qiang residents. It basically encompasses the richness and diversity of Chinese ethnic culture, forming a multicultural and pluralistic pattern in which the cultures of various ethnic groups intermingle.

Most of the current Chinese curriculum is often set up with the culture, history, geography, customs and values of the Han Chinese as the centre (Fan, 2015a). This mainstream cultural curriculum ignores the feelings and needs of other ethnic minority groups. In the current university piano education curriculum system, Western piano textbooks are used, and the piano teaching model for minority students is no different from that for Han students. However, from my more than ten years of teaching experience, it seems that the current university piano teaching ignores the fact that minority students themselves have a strong ethnic music and cultural background. They have been exposed to their own ethnic music since childhood and have been influenced by it more than Han students. The ethnic musical instruments they are good at

and the melodies they play are also unrelated to the piano. These factors make it more difficult for minority students to learn the piano.

Therefore, this thesis introduces the concept of multi-ethnic (Bennett, 1990) and multicultural coexistence (Banks, 1996) into the construction of piano courses in universities for ethnic minorities, expands on the existing basic piano course, and forms an expanded piano course that is built on the foundation of the existing piano course and addresses the current situation and problems of ethnic minority students. This will not only contribute to the deepening and development of theoretical research on piano courses for ethnic minorities in China, enriching course theory and ethnic education theory, and making due contributions to the establishment of a basic education curriculum system with Chinese characteristics; it will also provide new ideas for the reform of higher education curricula in ethnic minority areas, and provide local governments, education administrative departments and schools in ethnic minority areas with rational choices for the localized construction of higher education curriculum reform.

Research Question: What is the developed piano course for ethnic minority student?

Background of the existing piano teaching system in Chinese universities (Luo, 2010): the existing piano education courses are mainly based on Western music, and students gradually improve their technical skills and have a solid piano playing ability by learning piano works in different genres such as etudes, sonatas, polyphonic music and Chinese and foreign music.

Assessment criteria: The final examination is marked on the spot in the form of playing etudes, polyphonic, sonatas, music and vocal accompaniment. The length of the piano course is set for three years (6 semesters) and the lesson mode is one-to-four or one-to-three (2.4.4). According to the survey, the piano curriculum at ethnic minority universities is broadly in line with that of other general universities in Sichuan.

Since the above, it can be seen that in Chinese ethnic minority universities, ethnic minority students study the same set of piano lessons and the same assessment methods as Han Chinese students, but in my teaching over the past 10 years, I have found that ethnic minority students often find it very difficult and uninteresting to learn the piano, mainly for the following reasons:

- A. The vast majority of whom have no background in Western musical education.
- B. Most of one's ethnic instruments are played with

one hand and one is not comfortable playing with two hands.

- C. Own folk instruments without keyboard form
- D. Own folk music is based on monophonic melodies, which are difficult to adapt to the harmonic form of the piano.
- E. Because Tibetans and Qiang are good singers and dancers, their ethnic music has an extremely deep influence on their musical perceptions.

Therefore, when they are taught the same set of piano lessons as Han Chinese students in such a different cultural context, it is naturally more difficult for them to switch and accept than Han Chinese students, resulting in rejection and resistance to piano lessons and Western music.

Research Objective: To develop a piano course for ethnic minority students in an ethnic minority university.

Scope of the Study Site

Aba Tibetan and Qiang Autonomous Prefecture, Sichuan, China. Aba Tibetan and Qiang Autonomous Prefecture is located on the southeastern edge of the Qinghai-Tibet Plateau, in the northwestern part of Sichuan Province, between 100°0, ~104°7, East and 30°5, ~34°9, North. It borders Gansu and Qinghai to the north and northwest, Mianyang, Deyang and Chengdu to the east and southeast, Ya'an to the south and southwest, and Ganzi to the west. It is about 414 km long in the north and south, 360 km wide in the east and west, and covers an area of 84,242 square kilometres. By the end of 2021, the household population of Aba Tibetan and Qiang Autonomous Prefecture was 896,600. Among them, 537,100 were Tibetans and 166,500 were Qiang (Tourism Resources, 2019).

Aba Teachers University is the only higher education institution in Aba Tibetan and Qiang Autonomous Prefecture, founded in 1978, the School of Music and Dance, started in 1996 with the preparation of the music and dance education major, in 1997 officially enrolled music and dance education specialist students, pioneering the Sichuan provincial universities to hold music and dance complex education major. The College now offers three undergraduate programmes in musicology, dance and music performance, with 673 full-time undergraduate students. In terms of the piano discipline, the number of students who need to study piano for three years is about 400 per year, of which 60% are Han Chinese and 40% are from other ethnic minorities, with Tibetans and Qiang accounting for the largest proportion (Aba Teachers University Resources, 1978).

Participants

Experts (2): since the most authoritative university for the course of piano in the region where this research site is located is the Sichuan Conservatory of Music in China, one of them is from the professor of the piano department of the university. The other was from Aba Teachers' University, China, where he was the syllabus developer for the piano curriculum.

Teachers (2): since the location of this research is in Aba Teachers' University, China, two working piano teachers will be selected from this university. Different genders, title positions and teaching hours were covered in the selection.

Students (4): since the location of this research is in Aba Tibetan and Qiang Autonomous Prefecture, China, and Tibetan and Qiang students make up the largest percentage of the students, I chose students of the two ethnic groups, Tibetan and Qiang, as my research subjects. Different genders, musical backgrounds, and regions were covered in the selection. There were two Tibetan students and two Qiang students, one male and one female from each ethnic group.

Research Strengths

Being in an ethnic minority region of China and a piano teacher at the only university in Aba Tibetan and Qiang Autonomous Prefecture in Sichuan, China, I have first-hand research information. My research will result in an effective piano development course design that complements the existing piano curriculum and can probably be applied universally to most music colleges with ethnic minority students, providing some constructive thoughts on the construction and improvement of the piano teaching system for ethnic minorities in China.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses qualitative research (Zhu, 2024) methods to understand the current situation of university piano courses in China, as well as the educational policies, course programmes, and teacher preparation in Aba Tibetan and Qiang Autonomous Prefecture in Sichuan, China. As a teacher in the school, I was familiar with the environment of the selected sample school and understood the teaching history. In general, data collection was carried out at the end of each cycle at the expert, teacher, and student levels. In the process of writing the analysis, I still paid attention to relevant information, and whenever I found relevant information, I included new information in the analysis, so as to make the information as rich, complete, accurate and up-to-date as possible. Based on the background of Chinese ethnic minority

universities and the characteristics of piano course development, I integrated Banks' (1994) concept of multicultural education curriculum into the piano course for Chinese ethnic minorities, and based on the ADDIE teaching model (Figure 1), I researched the model of expanding the content of the piano course for ethnic minority students. The research framework can also be used as a reference for the future development of piano courses for ethnic minorities in China.

Figure 1: ADDIE Model.

Based on the ADDIE model (Zheng, Zhao, & Guo, 2021) and the research questions and research objectives of this research, I designed a total of seven steps in the research process (Figure 2), which is as follows: the first step is analysis, which involves interviewing all the participants, based on the interview questions. The second step is design, which involves designing a draft of teaching in response to the interview data from the previous step, and then interviewing experts to check and revise the draft. The third step was development. This is the development of the revised draft into a specific lesson plan that is given to the experts to check and revise again. The fourth step is implementation, with which the teaching plan is used to train 2 teachers for a 16-week teaching programme, each teacher teaching 2 students from different ethnic minorities. The fifth step was testing, testing 4 students with an exam that was scored by a peer reviewer. And after that

focus groups were conducted to interview 2 experts, 2 teachers and 4 students about their evaluation at the end of the teaching cycle. The sixth step is all data collection and organisation. The seventh step is the analysis of all the data and the development of the final results.

Figure 2: Research Process Picture.

RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH

In the first part of Analysis, I interviewed two piano experts, two piano teachers from the College of Music and Dance of Aba Teachers' University, and four ethnic minority students from the College of Music and Dance of Aba Teachers' University, and asked them about the current situation of ethnic minorities' learning the piano, as well as how to learn the piano in a better way. I recorded their answers, and then based on the collated interview data, the following four themes emerged through analysis:

1. The current situation of piano courses in Chinese universities
2. Difficulties in learning piano for ethnic minority students
3. Extended contents of piano courses for ethnic minority students
4. Assessment after the extended content

Each theme has a corresponding classification and explanation, and I have organised the keywords in the following table (Table 1):

Table 1: Thematic Analysis Table.

Core Category	Main Category	Initial Category
Status of Chinese University Piano Course	Teaching mode	1-1 1-3or4
	Student requirements	Performance Requirements Theoretical knowledge
	Course Properties	Professional courses Teach in line with the student's ability
Piano learning difficulties for ethnic minority students	Language barrier	
	Cultural differences	
	Attitude towards learning	Fear of difficulties Psychological resistance to completing exam tasks psychological barrier
	Weak foundation	
	Resource limitations	Learning resources are lacking Economic factors Lack of attention to the learning environment

Core Category	Main Category	Initial Category
Extended Piano Course for Ethnic Minority Students	Preparation stage	Respect for musical and cultural backgrounds
		Expanding Accessible Teaching Resources
		Establishment of a master-apprentice system
	Foundation stage	Understanding Language
		Selection of familiar folk music
		Step by step
		Syllabus-based learning
		Based on student interests and needs
	Development stage	Balancing Ethnic and Western Music
		Read the musical background
		Interactive Experience
		Collaborative learning in groups
	Advanced stage	Performance opportunity
Encourage creative improvisation		
Evaluation after extension of content	Follow the school's assessment criteria	
	Ethnic music for exams	
	Encouraging Personalising	
	Respect for ethnic minority cultural sensitivities	

The above data can be divided into four parts:

Part 1, the current status of piano courses in Chinese universities, shows that piano courses in Chinese universities generally adopt flexible teaching modes, including one-to-one, one-to-two or one-to-three teaching methods. Both Expert A and Expert B mentioned the advantages of this mode, i.e., the ability to teach students according to their aptitude, provide personalised instruction for students' different situations, and meet students' individual needs. Piano courses in Chinese universities have high requirements for students, not only do they need to have a certain level of piano playing ability, but they also need to have a general knowledge of music structure and other music knowledge and theory. In particular, Expert A points out that students should have an in-depth understanding of music aesthetics and general art theory. As a professional course, the main objective of the piano course is to train professionals in piano education. Expert A emphasised the importance of the piano course in Chinese universities, i.e. not only as a teaching of professional skills, but also focusing on the cultivation of piano education talents. Taken together, the piano courses in Chinese universities focus on individualised teaching, with comprehensive requirements for students' performance ability and theoretical knowledge, aiming to cultivate talents who can perform professionally in the field of piano education.

In Part 2, the section on the dilemmas of learning piano for ethnic minority students, the language barrier: one of the major challenges that ethnic minority students face when learning piano is the language barrier. As their mother tongue is not Chinese or English, this leads to difficulties in understanding sheet music and musical terms. Expert B, Teacher A and Student A all mentioned this issue, noting that the language barrier not only affects students' understanding of the content, but also increases learning pressure. Cultural differences

were another major barrier. The cultural and musical backgrounds of ethnic minority students differed significantly from those of Western classical music. As a result, they had trouble understanding and accepting piano music. Expert A, Expert B and Teacher A all emphasized the impact of cultural differences, which demonstrated the disparities in the understanding and acceptance of Western music among ethnic minority students since they had less exposure to it. Difficulties were common among ethnic minority students, and these were associated with cultural and linguistic barriers as well as a weak foundation. Expert A, Student C and Student D mentioned this, believing that fear and resistance could influence students' motivation and self-confidence in learning. Ethnic minority students also faced difficulties in adapting to teaching methods, particularly in basic skills like fingering and music recognition. Students A, B, C and D noted this, indicating that they usually began learning the piano at a relatively late age, leading to a weak foundation and the necessity for more practice and instruction. Resource limitations are another prominent issue for minority students. Due to their remote locations and economic conditions, they often lacked a proper learning environment and essential learning resources. Teacher B and Students A and C brought up this problem, pointing out that there might be traditional beliefs or prejudices regarding learning Western musical instruments in minority communities, along with differences in the learning atmosphere, family support and community involvement. To assist ethnic minority students in overcoming the difficulties they encounter in learning the piano, a comprehensive approach is required. This involves offering language support, respecting and integrating the cultural backgrounds of ethnic minorities, adjusting teaching methods to fit the students' foundation and requirements, and providing more resource support. Through these all-round measures, the learning effectiveness and motivation of ethnic minority students can be boosted, helping

them make progress in piano learning.

In Part 3, the extension of the piano curriculum for ethnic minority students focuses on ethnic minority cultural integration and personalised teaching. Cultural integration teaching enhances students' sense of cultural identity in piano learning by combining elements of ethnic minority music with piano teaching. Knowing the students' level of Mandarin in advance supports helping students to overcome language barriers and allows teachers to adjust their own pace of lessons and speaking speed so that students can better understand musical terms and scores. Teaching materials are selected with a focus on diversity and inclusiveness to ensure that they reflect the cultural elements and musical styles of ethnic minorities. Personalised lesson plans and repertoire choices, as well as interactive experiential activities, are designed to increase students' interest and engagement in learning.

In this section, I divided 4 stages. The first one is the preparation phase.

Respecting the cultural background: Recognizing and respecting the musical and cultural background of minority students constitutes the primary task in teaching. Expert A and Teacher A both highlighted the significance of understanding and respecting students' cultures when devising and adjusting teaching content.

Expanding teaching resources: To enable ethnic minority students to commence and continue their piano learning smoothly, it is essential to broaden the availability of teaching resources. Expert B and Teacher A pointed out that selecting teaching materials that match the students' proficiency levels and ensuring their easy access and usability are crucial for enhancing learning results.

Establishing a mentorship system: The mentorship teaching model offers personalized guidance and support to ethnic minority students, facilitating their better acquisition of piano-playing skills and musical knowledge. Both Teacher B and Student A concurred that the one-to-one approach is particularly vital for students with a weak foundation.

Understanding and adapting to students' language ability: Comprehending students' Mandarin proficiency and adjusting to their language ability are important aspects in the preparatory stage. Offering bilingual or multilingual teaching support can assist students in overcoming language barriers and grasping musical terms and scores more effectively. Expert A, Expert B and Teacher A all agreed that this is an effective means to help

ethnic minority students adapt to piano learning.

In conclusion, teaching in the preparatory stage should center around respecting and integrating the cultural backgrounds of minority students, expanding the availability of teaching resources, and establishing personalized mentoring connections. Meanwhile, understanding and adapting to students' language abilities plays a key role in helping them start piano learning successfully. Through these measures, ethnic minority students can be equipped with a solid learning foundation, and their interest and enthusiasm for piano learning can be aroused.

The second phase is the stage of laying the groundwork.

Regarding the Significance of Folk Music: Respondents commonly held the view that selecting folk music with which students are acquainted is of great significance for learning the piano. Expert A and Teacher A highlighted the importance of cultural integration and recommended the employment of teaching materials incorporating elements of ethnic music. This approach is aimed at diminishing students' resistance to the piano and facilitating their connection with piano learning. Expert B and Teacher B also mentioned the diversity and inclusiveness of teaching materials as a means to foster multicultural awareness and enable students to perceive the piano as a means of expressing their own culture.

Concerning the Step-by-Step Teaching Methodology: Interviewees generally concurred that the step-by-step teaching approach is highly efficacious for ethnic minority students in learning the piano. Expert A proposed gradually incorporating more challenging pieces into the technical skills curriculum. Students also indicated a preference for an easy-to-difficult teaching method, believing it would assist them in progressively adapting to piano learning.

On Laying a Foundation in Accordance with the Syllabus: Both Expert A and Teacher B underlined the importance of establishing a foundation based on the piano course syllabus to guarantee that students obtain the requisite basic skills and knowledge. Student D concurred that the initial step was to undergo a mindset transformation and practice more assiduously.

Regarding Curriculum Design Based on Interests and Needs: Both Expert B and Teacher A mentioned the importance of devising the curriculum in line with students' interests and requirements. Teacher B further elaborated that the materials should be

flexible to accommodate the specific situations and needs of students. Students also expressed a preference for materials and teaching methods that mirrored their interests and needs.

In terms of Student Feedback: Student feedback manifested a strong demand for familiarity with the national repertoire and support for a step-by-step teaching approach and personalized learning. They also emphasized the significance of laying a solid foundation and implementing interest- and needs-based curriculum design.

In summary, the respondents agreed that in order to improve the effectiveness of piano learning for ethnic minority students, they should select ethnic repertoire that they are familiar with, adopt a step-by-step teaching methodology, build a foundation based on the syllabus, and at the same time design the curriculum based on students' interests and needs, and adopt diversified teaching methods in order to personalise learning. This teaching strategy not only helps students overcome cultural and language barriers, but also stimulates their interest in learning and improves their learning results.

The third stage is skill development.

Balancing Ethnic and Western Music: Expert A advised against over-reliance on Western repertoire as a guide, while Teacher A emphasised finding a balance between the two. Students also expressed a preference for incorporating familiar folk music in their performance of pieces while embracing Western repertoire in their basic exercises.

Read the musical background: Experts believe that both teachers and students need to read more about the background of music. Whether it is Western music or folk music, it is necessary to understand the history and culture behind the music in order to better interpret it.

Importance of Interactive Experiences: Interactive experiences were considered to be an effective means of increasing students' interest and engagement in learning. Both Expert B and Teacher A advocated designing interactive learning activities such as music games, role-playing, and improvisation to enhance students' engagement and creativity. Teacher B further recommended contextual simulation teaching to enhance the interactivity and fun of learning by simulating different performance scenarios and musical styles.

Group Cooperation and Collaborative Learning: Group cooperation and collaborative learning

are important ways to enhance students' social skills and teamwork. Teacher B encourages the enhancement of student interaction and collaboration through group learning and ensemble playing. Students generally agreed that learning with other students could enhance each other's learning and contribute to cultural integration. Student D particularly mentioned that learning with classmates of different nationalities could be positively influenced to improve their piano skills.

In summary, the skill development stage should focus on the balance between ethnic and western music, and increase students' participation and creativity through diversified teaching methods and interactive experiential activities. At the same time, group cooperation and collaborative learning not only enhance students' social skills, but also promote mutual learning and growth among students from different cultural backgrounds. This integrated approach helps students develop holistically, both in terms of technical skills and musical expression.

The fourth stage is the advanced stage.

Importance of performance opportunities: Providing performance opportunities was seen as crucial to enhancing students' sense of achievement and self-confidence. Specialist B emphasised the importance of allowing students to experience a sense of achievement in playing through performances in school concerts and community events. Teacher B advocated project-based learning, such as preparing for concerts and participating in music competitions, so that students could improve their musical skills and performance abilities through practice.

Encouragement of creative improvisation: Creative improvisation was considered an important means of developing students' creativity and musical expression. Both Specialist A and Teacher A advocated the inclusion of interactive elements in teaching and encouraging students to improvise or compose, even if it was a short measure, to enhance students' engagement and creativity. Expert B and Teacher B also endorsed this perspective. They were of the opinion that when students are spurred to cultivate their individual musical styles and engage in music composition, their comprehension and manifestation of music would be elevated.

To sum it up, the design of the advanced piano programme ought to place emphasis on practical and creative learning. Through furnishing abundant performance opportunities and motivating

improvisation, students can not merely enhance their technical proficiency but also foster a more profound degree of musical expression and cultural understanding. This teaching method facilitates students in developing a distinctive musical style and augments their musical creativity and self-assurance.

The fourth part is about the assessment component of the extended content of piano for ethnic minority students. Maintenance of Uniform Assessment Standards: In the assessment of the post-extension content of the piano programme, the school's consistent assessment standards play a fundamental role. They ensure that all students are evaluated under identical criteria, thus safeguarding the fairness of the assessment. Expert A, Expert B and Teacher A all emphasized that the consistency of assessment standards is an essential part of the assessment process. Diversified Assessment Methods (Zhuang, 1997): To more comprehensively reflect the cultural traits and musical abilities of ethnic minority students, the utilization of ethnic music can be regarded as an alternative to the traditional assessment repertoire. Specialist A and Specialist B advocated the adoption of diversified assessment methods to overcome the limitations of a single testing approach, and Teacher A also backed such diversified testing.

Encouraging Students' Aesthetic and Creative Endeavours: Granting extra marks for students' aesthetic analysis and creative abilities during the assessment can arouse their enthusiasm for creativity and deepen their understanding of music. Both Expert A and Teacher B concurred that students should be encouraged and rewarded with extra credit for their aesthetic analyses and piano compositions of ethnic music. Valuing Encouragement and Cultural Sensitivity: Expert B stressed that the aim of assessment is not merely to test competence, but also to motivate students to keep learning and making progress. Meanwhile, the cultural backgrounds of students should be respected throughout the assessment process to prevent cultural bias and guarantee the cultural sensitivity of the assessment. In conclusion, the assessment of the piano programme after its content expansion should adhere to a unified assessment standard while introducing diversified assessment methods to better mirror students' cultural characteristics and musical abilities. By encouraging students' aesthetic analyses and compositions, as well as focusing on encouragement and cultural sensitivity in assessment, students' comprehensive musical literacy can be assessed more comprehensively and their innovation and progress in music learning can be promoted.

Extended Piano Course Content for Ethnic Minority Students Design

In the piano syllabus, the following extensions were designed in this study for ethnic minority students (Zhong, 2000):

Cultural background: the importance of understanding the cultural and musical characteristics of ethnic minorities is emphasised, and it is proposed that basic knowledge and understanding be enhanced by reading relevant books and articles.

Technical orientation: It was proposed to add 10 ethnic minority piano pieces to enrich the existing teaching materials and to encourage students to compose freely according to their own level.

Develop

After feedback from experts and teachers, the programme was adjusted as follows (Zhang, 2000):

Cultural background: On the basis of the teachers' understanding of minority cultures, they added explanations of Western music, distributed background information on the music in advance, and adjusted the language of instruction to take into account the students' proficiency in Mandarin.

Technical orientation: Grading the difficulty level of ethnic minority piano repertoire and encouraging the study of songs from different ethnic groups in order to increase the diversity of the repertoire.

Teaching Progress: It is recommended to keep in line with the school syllabus and ensure synchronisation with other students' teaching progress.

Implementation

Based on the previous analyses and developments, the following extensions were implemented (Ou, 1998):

Basic Piano Theory: While teaching basic piano sitting and touching the keys, cultural background learning was added by providing reference books on ethnic minority cultures and musical characteristics.

Piano Technique Training: Maintaining the original syllabus, teaching staccato and legato techniques.

Piano Piece Performance Training: no modification in the teaching of exercises, using the traditional exercises; in the performance of pieces, adding ethnic minority piano repertoire, choosing the appropriate repertoire according to the level of the students.

Detailed Implementation of Extended Content

Table 2: The School's Original Piano Course Syllabus (freshman year, 16 weeks).

No.	Course content	Class Schedule
1	Basic Piano Theory: Explaining the basic sitting posture and touching the keys of the piano	4 weeks
2	Piano Technique Training: Training in staccato and legato	4 weeks
3	Piano Piece Performance Training: Finger training in piano works (Etudes)	4 weeks
4	Training in playing piano works: Finger training in the performance of piano works	4 weeks

As can be seen from this table 2, each 4 weeks is a unit and there are 4 units in total. The first unit is Basic Piano Theory. This unit is a theory class. The second unit is Piano Technique Training, which consists of teaching staccato and legato. The third unit is Piano Piece Performance Training, which teaches how to play the Etudes. The fourth unit is the second step of the Piano Piece Performance Training, which is about finger training in the performance of piano pieces. Each unit corresponds to a 4-week course.

(2) Expansion of the contents (Table 3): In the original piano syllabus of the school, on the premise of not changing the teaching programme, in the first 4 weeks of the theory course, a cultural background session was added, i.e., on the basis of understanding the cultural background of the ethnic minority students and being familiar with the characteristics of the music of the ethnic minorities, a session of explaining the Western music was added to the students. Because ethnic minority students do not know enough about western music, and in advance, all the western music to be taught, its background, introduction, authors, etc. will be distributed to the students in the form of electronic resources. In the language session, students were

interviewed in advance whether they were proficient in Mandarin, and if they were not too proficient, teachers were advised to slow down their speech and use simple language during the lesson. In this cycle, I prepared reference books with ethnic minority cultural backgrounds for teachers to read (He, 2011).

In the second 4-week course on piano technique, the original piano syllabus called for teaching piano staccato and continuo, and in this session the expert recommended no modification.

In the third 4-week course on finger training in piano works (etudes), the experts recommended that no modifications be made and that the original etudes (e.g. Czerny, Hanon, etc.) be used as the content of the course.

In the fourth 4-week course, the original piano syllabus calls for the teaching of playing methods in works. In this session, Ethnic Piano Songs are added, and are taught according to the level of difficulty recommended by the experts, and according to the student's own level. (There is no hard and fast rule here as to which piece is to be taught, the teacher will lay out the repertoire according to the student's level of playing).

Table 3: Extensions Piano Course Syllabus.

No.	Course content	class schedule	Expanded Content
1	Basic Piano Theory: Explaining the basic sitting posture and touching the keys of the piano	4 weeks	Understand the cultural background and musical characteristics of ethnic minorities and read reference books
2	Piano Technique Training: Training in staccato and legato	4 weeks	Same
3	Piano Piece Performance Training: Finger training in piano works (Etudes)	4 weeks	Same
4	Training in playing piano works: Finger training in the performance of piano works	4 weeks	Piano Music for Ethnic Minorities

A: Ethnic Minority Cultural Background Reference Books: Take 6 books as an example, covering the music and culture of China's ethnic minorities, historical stories, language studies, and historical information about ethnic minorities in Southwest China.

B: Differences between Ethnic Piano Songs and Western Music:

In ethnic music, the key is established in three ways: firstly, by looking at the main tone of the whole melody, secondly, by looking at the termination of each phrase,

and thirdly, by looking at the final termination. When they are very uniform, the tonic modality is single, and when they are not, the tonal modality takes on a variety of styles and natures. According to the modal structure of the European major/minor system, the terminating note and the terminating chord must be do or la and their major/minor major triads. It is not arbitrary. But there is a peculiar phenomenon in the Han modes: the arbitrariness of the terminating tone. Whether it is a half termination or a full termination, it can be terminated selectively and arbitrarily within the

range of five tones, which makes the ethnic modes also have the characteristic of multiplicity. This is of great theoretical significance and practical value to our understanding and management of folk modes (Liu, 2007).

The first piece, Daughter-in-Law's Bitterness, is in the Chinese tuning of: bB major pentatonic+perfect 4th. The second piece "The Golden Sun" is in the Chinese mode of e minor pentatonic. These two pieces are the music of China's ethnic minorities, which show different forms from Western music in terms of sentence structure and tonal modulation.

Sentence Structure: These two pieces all adopt the structure of a piece of music, and in the sentence structure, they all adopt the sentence structure of the 'Qi-Cheng-Zhuan-He' (Qiao, 2019). The Golden Sun (Figure 4) is a traditional four-sentence structure, while The Daughter-in-law's Bitterness (Figure 3) is expanded on the basis of the four-sentence structure, which is formed through the repetition of changes in the first sentence. Chinese and western music are in the same compositional structure, but the western music is very rich in the use of the two-sentence, three-sentence, four-sentence, and multiple-sentence structure, but in the classical period, the even-numbered sentences are mainly used, and the number of bars in each phrase is mainly 4 or 8 bars, which pays attention to the symmetry and neatness, and in the Romantic period, the use of odd-numbered phrases is gradually increasing. In China's traditional folk music, the four-sentence phrase of 'Qi-Cheng-Zhuan-He' is widely used, and in the more developed four-sentence phrases, the third phrase is often split into a row of stomping phrases, which deepens and expands the function of the 'Zhuan'.

Tonality: Western classical music is dominated by the major and minor modes system, which consists of seven tones that move around a central tone (Nei & Guan, 2004). Western major and minor keys are natural, harmonic and melodic. Major keys are often used in natural major keys, while minor keys are often used in harmonic minor keys. Pentatonic and heptatonic modes are commonly used in folk music, and heptatonic modes are based on pentatonic modes with the addition of partials. Pentatonic modulation is composed of five tones arranged in pure fifths, and each of the five tones in the modulation can be used as the main tone. The seven-tone modulation is based on the five tones of the five-tone modulation, and by adding different partials, it is again divided into Ching-Yue, Ya-Yue, and Yan-Yue (Du, 2002). The biggest difference between Western major and minor tunes and ethnic tuning is the dominant tone;

Western major and minor tunes use the first tone of the tuning as the central tone, while all five tones in the ethnic tuning can be used as the dominant tone. 'The Golden Sun' is in e -Yu five-tone(e - g - a - b - d). 'Daughter-in-law's Bitterness' is in bB -Gong plus Qingjue six-tone(b - c - d - e - f - g).

Other ethnic minority cultural background reference books will be reflected in the further readings.

羌族
Qiang

86. 媳妇苦
"Daughter-in-law's Bitterness"

羌族民歌
Qiang folk song

Figure 3: The Daughter-in-law's Bitterness.

Take this Qiang music song "Daughter-in-law's Bitterness" as an example, the Qiang people are mainly distributed in Aba Tibetan and Qiang Autonomous Prefecture in Sichuan (Chen, 2017). The Qiang language belongs to the Qiang branch of the Tibeto-Burman language family of the Sino-Tibetan language family, and has two major dialects: southern and northern. The majority of the Qiang people understand Chinese, and the Chinese language is commonly used. The Qiang have a long history, and there are already records of the Qiang in the oracle bone inscriptions. The Qiangs are mainly engaged in agriculture, with corn as the main crop, but also grow barley, wheat, buckwheat and beans, and also engage in animal husbandry, with cattle, horses and sheep as the main livestock. Mountain songs are the most popular type of songs among the Qiang, mostly sung during labour and in the mountains and fields, in the form of solos and duets. This song was sung by a woman who was forced to get married in another country. Its lyrics are: "The flowers of the goat's horns are so bright and colourful, and the flowers by the riverside are open, but I am the daughter of a bitter fate, who was married off to a faraway country, and I am so sad in my heart (Du, 2014).

50. 金色的太阳
"The Golden Sun"

Tibetan folk song
藏族民歌

a Lively ♩=92 活泼

The musical score is written for piano in 2/4 time with a key signature of one sharp (F#). It consists of four sections labeled a, b, c, and d. Section 'a' is marked 'Lively' and '活泼' with a tempo of ♩=92. It begins with a mezzo-piano (mp) dynamic. Section 'b' starts with a mezzo-forte (mf) dynamic. Section 'c' includes a mezzo-piano (mp) dynamic and a forte (f) dynamic. Section 'd' is marked mezzo-forte (mf). The score includes various musical notations such as slurs, ties, and fingerings (e.g., 1, 2, 3, 4, 5). There are also decorative symbols (snowflake-like icons) at the bottom of some measures.

Figure 4: The Golden Sun.

"The Golden Sun": The Tibetans are one of the ethnic minorities in China with a long history and developed culture, living mainly in the Tibet Autonomous Region and the Tibetan autonomous prefectures and counties in Sichuan, Qinghai, Gansu and Yunnan provinces (Yang, 2021). The Tibetan language belongs to the Tibeto-Burman group of the Sino-Tibetan language family, and there are three dialect areas, namely Weizang, Kang and Amdo. The Tibetans call folk songs and dances "Lu Xie", and according to the custom of this people, folk songs and dances cannot be separated, and the traditional concepts are divided into three different forms. "Lu", "Xie", "Free Style".

"Lu" is mostly an apprentice song, not accompanied by physical movements, and therefore has a freer rhythm, often with a loose plate, a higher register, and a gorgeous tune. The "Lu" category of folk songs includes "Li Lu", "Chang Lu" and other categories, mostly solo and duet songs. The "Xie" category of folk songs includes "Cuisine Xie", "Fruit Xie", "Chang Xie", "Ba Xie", "Dui Xie" and other varieties, mostly dance songs (Du, 2014).

This is a popular Tibetan dance song in the Qinghai area, the rhythm is cheerful and lively, the song sings: "Chairman Mao's light shines on the snowy

mountains, and since then the Tibetan people have been liberated." In the 1960s, this song was used in the music and dance epic "The East is Red", and then spread throughout the country (Fan, 2015b).

Summary of the evaluation and implementation of the extended content:

Without changing the original marking criteria, ethnic minority students were allowed to choose an ethnic minority piano piece from the extended content as one of the examination pieces in the final examination. This change is intended to assess students' mastery of the extended content and to encourage them to demonstrate their cultural characteristics.

Marking Scheme: The marking scheme is based on a 100-point scale and is divided into six grades from A to F. A mark of 60 or above is regarded as a pass. The grading basis includes accuracy, completeness, technical level, musical expression and understanding of the work.

Results of the assessment: Four ethnic minority students took the final examination and their average scores were all in grades A and B, indicating that they not only met the assessment criteria but also performed well.

Focus group discussion: After the assessment, a focus group discussion was conducted with the participation of two experts, two teachers and four ethnic minority students. The topic of the discussion was students' feelings and suggestions about the extended content of the piano programme.

Interview data results: Student feedback: students felt that the extension content helped them greatly by reducing their fear of piano learning, increasing their interest in playing ethnic minority music, and feeling that their teachers respected and understood their cultural backgrounds.

Expert assessment: The assessment results showed that the extension was very effective, students' interest increased significantly, the choice of repertoire was appropriate to the students' level, the original syllabus was not changed, and the synchronised progress with other students was maintained.

Teacher observation: The teacher found that prior knowledge of the students' cultural background and language level was helpful, and that the students became more motivated to practise after their interest in the piano increased. However, the students still need to improve their creativity.

Summary: Taking into account the feedback from students, experts and teachers, as well as the assessment scores, it can be clearly concluded that the extended content of the piano programme had a positive impact on the ethnic minority students. It not only improved their interest and skills, but also promoted their enthusiasm for piano learning and cultural identity. Future work could further explore how these positive outcomes can be extended to a wider range of pedagogical practices to achieve a more inclusive and diverse music education.

DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In the 11 years that I have been engaged in piano education for ethnic minority students, I have seen that many ethnic minority students have positive attitudes towards the piano but cannot find a way to do so; some are negative, thinking that they are not good at learning the piano; and some are indifferent, thinking that it is just a matter of completing the examination tasks. However, I have been trying to find a suitable piano teaching method and content for this group, so that they can learn the piano in a better and more adaptable way. I wanted to break down the lack of confidence in piano learning from the conception, and incorporate ethnic music elements as much as possible under the premise of retaining the piano technique learning, so that they can accept the course more easily. Therefore, this research

was conducted by incorporating ethnic cultural elements and repertoire into the piano course as an extension of the piano course for ethnic minority students, and this content significantly increased the interest and participation of ethnic minority students. By analysing the results of focus group discussions and assessments, we found that students not only made progress in the technical level, but also gained significant improvement in cultural identity and self-expression.

As for the teaching methods, the personalised and culturally sensitive teaching methods implemented in the research showed good adaptability. By adapting the language of instruction and providing background information, students' language barrier and cultural difference problems were effectively alleviated. This suggests that flexibility and diversity in teaching methods are essential in meeting the needs of students from different backgrounds.

In this part of the assessment method, this research included Ethnic Piano Songs in the assessment, which is a useful supplement to the traditional assessment method. This innovation not only examines students' mastery of Western classical music, but also evaluates their understanding and expression of their own culture, reflecting the cultural sensitivity and comprehensiveness of the assessment. Adding optional content on top of the original assessment reflects the diversity of assessment methods.

In my opinion, teaching methods are always just methods, and the most important thing is that the confidence and initiative of ethnic minority students can be encouraged and guided through teaching methods. The reason why this extension of the piano course for ethnic minority students is placed in the first semester is because I hope to be able to stimulate the musical talent that ethnic minority students already possess from the very beginning through such a study, by generating interest and initiative in the piano. In the past, there were a lot of Chinese music for reference and study, but usually these pieces were difficult and almost impossible for ethnic minority students to play at their piano level. So they initially had to choose Western music to learn, which caused them to resist and give up piano learning in the next four years. So I hope that through this course, the ethnic minority students will be able to love their own ethnic music culture and at the same time learn the piano very actively.

In the current literature that I have checked, there are many people researching the musical heritage of minorities and the cultural heritage of

minorities (Zhao & Qin, 2012). There is also a lot of research from the main body of university education, hoping to reflect the importance of minority culture from the course (Li, 2018). However, there is no literature to show how to achieve the importance of minority culture in the university piano course, and how to make minority students learn the piano better. Therefore, I hope that through this research, minority students can better utilise their musical talent through the piano course, and I also hope that through university music education we can cultivate more minority musical talents for the future.

Research Limitations

Although this research has achieved positive results in enhancing the interest and participation of ethnic minority students in learning piano, there are still some shortcomings.

Sample problem: Because the place of this study is the only university in the Aba Prefecture region of Sichuan, China, the sample size involved is small and limited to a specific area, so it may not be able to comprehensively represent the situation of all ethnic minority students.

Depth and Breadth of Cultural Elements: Because the ethnic minorities targeted in this study were the Qiang and Tibetan, more attention was paid to these two ethnic groups when incorporating cultural elements of ethnic minorities, but other ethnic groups were also involved in piano scores, but the depth and diversity of the music of the different ethnic groups may not adequately represent the uniqueness of the culture of each ethnic group (Zhou, 1998).

Teaching content: In the advanced content section of the interview data, students are expected to have a willingness to compose on their own. For example, students were encouraged to improvise or compose, which would not only increase their participation, but by encouraging students to create various forms of music, students could explore different ways of musical expression and enhance their musical creativity. However, in the implementation process, because the research object is a freshman student, for the piano is still in the primary stage, more is to complete the teaching part of the piano foundation, so this creative part they failed to reflect (Yu & Xie, 2006).

Recommendations

Future research could consider further expanding the teaching content to include more musical elements and repertoire from more ethnic groups. This will not only enrich teaching resources, but also

provide students with a broader cultural perspective and learning experience. Explore more teaching methods, such as interactive learning, project-based learning and reverse classroom, to cater for different learning styles and needs (Li, 1991).

Students' active learning capabilities and innovative thinking can be further boosted by means of diversified teaching approaches. It is necessary to continuously refine the assessment system and contemplate the introduction of more diverse assessment criteria and methods, like self-assessment, peer assessment, and process evaluation. This will facilitate a more comprehensive evaluation of students' learning achievements and foster their all-round development.

Enhancing teachers' comprehension of and skills in multicultural teaching and learning, and elevating their professionalism and teaching proficiency is crucial. Through professional development, teachers can carry out personalized and culturally sensitive teaching more efficiently. Exploring the potential of integrating music education with other subject fields, such as history, literature, and art, should be given priority. Interdisciplinary integration can offer students a more holistic learning experience and contribute to holistic education.

Leveraging modern educational technologies, such as online learning platforms and multimedia tools, can supply students with more convenient learning channels and richer learning resources. The integration of technology is beneficial for enhancing teaching efficiency and improving students' learning experiences. The positive impacts of the extended piano course on ethnic minority students, as demonstrated in this study, are clearly recorded. By integrating cultural context, technical guidance, and creative motivation, it not only augmented students' musical abilities but also fortified their cultural confidence and creativity. In the future, we anticipate extending these achievements to a broader spectrum of educational domains and making contributions to the attainment of educational equality and diversity.

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